

WOMEN AND COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: THE UBURU EXPERIENCE, 1800-2015

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Abstract: *Women are active members of the society who have contributed immensely to the growth and development of their societies. Uburu women have contributed in no small measure to community development. This paper examines women and community development in Nigeria: The Uburu experience, 1800 to 2015. The study stressed on the following objectives; the land and people of Uburu in relation to gender roles, gender roles disparity in Uburu community, and impact of women in Uburu community. The study adopted gender complementarity theory as theoretical frame work, qualitative approach and use of primary and secondary sources of history as the research methods which aided in critical observations. The major findings of the study include that women played active role in the development of Uburu community. Women in Uburu were constraints by unequal access to farm land, inequality, economic and political discrimination and other challenges. It is on this premise that the study recommends gender equality, equal access to land use and equal economic, political and educational opportunities as measures to address the challenges militating against effective women contribution in the development of Uburu community. Special child care/security allowance was also recommended. Women voice should be heard in all endeavours for maximum success. Plans should be carefully crafted and carried out to ensure that the objectives of women developmental progress are met.*

Introduction

The gift of women and more specifically, God's endowment of female with responsibility for the regeneration of humankind is one of the

mysteries of human life that is both the most important and awe-inspiring. Women are essential to the functioning of every human society. Since the beginning of time, Nigerian

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women have made significant contributions to the nation's socioeconomic, political, cultural, and religious growth. These contributions have been invaluable. Women make up around 65% of Nigeria's total population and are well recognized for the significant contributions they make in a variety of spheres, including those of motherhood, education, care giving, and leadership (Ngene, 2022).

Odi (2021) posits that where women's contributions are not valued, it will be difficult, if not impossible to advance humans' civilization. He further stressed that any society which neglects such a big number of human resource potential cannot accomplish any meaningful development. To Ijere (1991), women are the backbone of community development and may be found working in agriculture and other fields. When they aren't there to care for their kids, spouses, relatives, friends, and guests, it's noticed. He came to the conclusion that if women are excluded from the process of family and community development, it would fail.

Awortu & Michael (2019) posited that women are active members of society who have contributed immensely to community development. Women in Africa carry significant propositions of the work load in food crop cultivation, animal husbandry, food processing and distribution. They combined all these with their sex and gender roles of procreation, early socialization and child care. The foregoing

remark assumes, without saying it implicitly, that women are valuable assets for development. Women in rural areas have made significant contributions to the progress and development of their communities, thus, it would be reasonable to posit that women in general are embodiment of development. Women occupy important and decisive place in the economic, political and socio-cultural life of Uburu community. Their importance is perceptible both in traditional and modern sectors, not only as mothers in society, but also by their contributions to the quality of day to day life. Unfortunately, for so many years, their importance has been overlooked and neglected. Attoe (2002) maintained that literatures on Nigeria's national development are relatively silent on the roles of women in development. Yusuf (in Badejo, 1985) argued that "looking back at the political evolution of the country, an independent observer would hastily conclude that women have contributed next to nothing in this very important aspect of human life". The contributions made by women on a global scale were not acknowledged until relatively recently, when the United Nations declared the period from 1976 to 1985 to be "the decade for women." This declaration made it obligatory for governments to prioritize the issue of women as an essential part of national development. On the other hand, a more in-depth research indicates that Uburu women played a major part in the growth of the community. This

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finding is supported by the evidence shown in the previous paragraph. Prior to colonization, women took part in a variety of pre-colonial occupations, including the manufacturing of salt, hunting and gathering, and internal and external trading. They were active in a variety of activities throughout the colonial and post-colonial periods, including the development of co-operative organizations and unions, the financing of day care and elementary schools, the promotion of cleanliness programmes, and more. Mothers, as the major caretakers of their families, have a vital role not only in the development of their children, including the education and socialization of their children, but also in leadership and governance.

Although women were perceived to be weak, they have come a long way in proving their strength in different capacities. The factors militating against the contributions of women in community development has led to economic, political and socio-cultural setbacks. This study will identify the factors that delay and inhibit the contributions of women in the development of Uburu and recommend measures that will promote effective women participation in the development of Uburu.

Theoretical Framework

Gender complementarity theory was adopted. The theory explains the complementary role of both sexes in the progress and development of humanity. Gender complementarity theory explained that no single individual is

independent. It stresses mutual interdependence among human beings. Afigbo A.E (1991) subscribes to this gender complementarity theory to achieve a balance in the society. He posits that when we are talking of the role of women, we are talking of male and female harmoniously complementing themselves through women contributing those things which only women can contribute and men those they can contribute. It is only by so doing we can satisfy the requirements of the law of balance and complementarity on which much that happens around us are based. He equally pointed out two major roles performed by women which are motherhood and building of the society.

Onwuzurike, E. (2003) also subscribed to this gender complementarity theory to build a harmonious and happy society. Onwuzurike revealed that the society understood the indispensability of the womenfolk hence both sexes lived on complimentary rather than on competitive lines. It took the existence of the two sexes living together to create a harmonious and happy society. Onwuzurike equally opined that the traditional society did not accept the idea of equality of the two sexes, yet it did not regard the female as inferior or servant to the male. The society operated on a sex based division of labor which actually spelt out the functions and privileges of each of the two sexes.

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Sokari- George, G. (2003) also subscribed to this gender complementarity theory in the society. He postulated that women are not equal to men nor are they inferior to men; both sexes need each other and therefore are complementary. Relating the theory to our study becomes necessarily, if we evaluate the developments and gradual changes that have taken place concerning women in the political, economic and socio- cultural spheres in Uburu community when compared to the past. At present, Uburu women are educated like the men and are found in various sectors of life. They also have some organizations that champion's women advancement.

Land and People of Uburu in Relation to Gender Roles

Uburu is a community in Ohaozara Local Government Area of Ebonyi State. It is one of the three ancient communities that made up Ohaozara Local Government Area. Uburu community is made up of four autonomous communities: Uburu, Enu-Uburu, Etitu Uburu and Eweze Uburu. Uburu is known for her deep cultural civility, hospitality and rich mineral deposit like the popular Uburu salt lake, known among the natives as Mmahi. Uburu has the highest deposit of salt in old Eastern Nigeria and the motto of Ebonyi State "Salt of the Nation" is derived from the rich salt deposit in Uburu and other places (Obasi, 2017).

Uburu is bounded in the South by Okposi, East by Okpanku, Oduma and Nkerefi community of

Nkanu East, North by Onicha and Isu communities, in the West by Mpu and Akeze communities. Uburu belongs to the Igbo people of Southeastern Nigeria. Being one of the Igbo groups, Uburu people face the general problem of uncertainty which surrounds generally Igbo history of origin.

However, every society holds on to one oral tradition or another with regards to its origin. From oral tradition, the history of the origin and settlement of Uburu is essentially the history of several migrations and the period of this settlement is uncertain since the settlement of each of the fourteen villages of Uburu community occurred over a long period of time (Odi, 2021). Indeed, the tradition of origin, migrations and settlements of Uburu people like many Igbo communities is equally constipated with lengthy migrations and this has been confirmed by various studies on her history. They include J.D. Hamilton's "Intelligent report" on Uburu clan (sic) of Afikpo division of the Ogoja province in May, 1939.

Hamilton (1939) opines that the fourteen village which makeup Uburu community migrated into this new land of salt from different communities in Igbo land to settle in this area discovered by an Agwu Agbor hunter. Ogwu village became the first settlers of what is today Uburu community. Other villages Umuchima, Mgbom, Umuobuna, Umuaneketa, Umugwuoke, Umuanum, Amegu, Urobo, Uhuaba, Umuodigbo, Umunaga and Ihenu migrated later

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having heard about the salt spring and its economic promise, through their wandering heroes.

Uburu is an agrarian society that cultivates crops such as yam, plantain, palm fruits, vegetables, cassava, cocoyam, maize, banana among others. Uburu people are also involved in hunting and gathering, gun powder production, fishing, salt making, rearing of domestic animals etc. Uburu has the oldest hospital in the entire West African region, Presbyterian Joint Hospital Uburu established in 1913 (Connel, 1939). Uburu Adu Nshiegbe kingdom, as it is popularly called is situated on a plain land. The natural features include a flowing stream (Esu River). It flows from its upper course in Akpugo Nkanu in Neighboring Enugu State. Esu River divided Uburu community into two halves. One half is mainly for settlement while the other half is the sparsely populated farmlands. The fertile land promotes agriculture and other economic activities such as hunting, palm oil production, gun powder production and salt making from the Uburu salt lake.

It was the economic potentials of Uburu that attracted traders, farmers and migrant workers from neighboring kingdoms and communities. While Uburu women were busy in salt production, the men specialize in the production of gun powder and farming. Because of its salt, gun powder production and its strategic location for trade with the North,

Uburu developed into one of Igbo land's great periodic fairs and also one of its gateways for import (Okpara, 2006).

In traditional Uburu society, there is gender division of roles. Yam production has always been regarded as the exclusive preserve of men possibly because of the strain involved in its cultivation. While the men take responsibility for clearing the farm land, the women undertake to burn the bush and assist in carrying the yam seedlings to their various destinations for planting by the men. Weeding is the duty of women who also provide the vanguard for carrying the proceeds of the harvest, at times by head porter age to the house and to the markets where there is surplus production. Salt production and the production of cassava are the main occupation of women. Ngene (2022) posits that salt making was totally left for Uburu women. The salt industry was and is a source of pride to Uburu women, and it gives them sense of belonging. They do not struggle land with men, because God has buttered their bread by the presence of the salt brine, where they can equally get from salt production what men get from yam and rice production. It is Uburu custom and tradition that women don't struggle land with men.

[[[Gender Roles Disparity in Uburu Community

Gender is not accurately captured by the traditional male and female dichotomy of sex.

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Studies show the different experiences of genders across many domains including family life, occupation or careers, education, interest etc. The traditional Uburu society did not accept the idea of gender parity, yet it did not regard the female as inferior or servants to the male. Uburu society operated a sex based division of labour which actually spelt out the functions and privileges of each gender.

Hunting and Gathering

Hunting and gathering represents the oldest form of human adaptation. Hunting and gathering live in 'bands'. It is not acceptable for women to participate in hunting, and there is an emphasis on cooperation and sharing between both genders. Subsistence in pre-colonial Uburu civilization was mostly attained by hunting, fishing, and gathering natural plants and animals, as well as other foods such as honey. Although men undertake the majority of the hunting with firearms and bows, women and children nevertheless contribute significantly to the household's food supply via their own hunting and the collecting of natural resources. Women and children were involved in trapping small animals and birds. Women do most of the snail collecting. Uburu population relies heavily on subsistence hunting for their source of bush meats (Odi, 2021).

Most professional hunters, according to Okike (2021), have their own firearms; amateur and young hunters may or may not. Younger, occasional hunters may borrow firearms from

more experienced hunters in exchange for a cut of the catch. Uburu subsistence hunters make use of homemade muzzle-loaders, snares, traps, dogs, and even fire to flush out game. Hunters may go out on their own or with friends. One may go on a solo hunt at any time of day or night, in any kind of forest cover, or even in the secondary growth near farms. Many farmers also like hunting and/or trapping, so they divide their time between the two. When searching for wild creatures, many people used dogs.

On market days, the hunter and his assistants would carry the meat into town, while sometimes women buyers would trek from one camp to the next to purchase meat. In Uburu, there are three primary types of community hunting practiced; the use of fire to smoke out animals, seasonal group hunting using guns, combining of vegetation to drive out animals which are then killed with clubs and cutlasses.

The vast majority of gun-toting hunters also use traps. Farmers who do not use firearms to hunt, as well as women and children also used traps. The traps set around farms are checked daily or at least as frequently as the farmer or his family makes a trip there. Structures located in the woods are routinely checked once a day. To steal or steal an animal from another person's trap is a highly severe offence in Uburu. As the major food gatherers, women play a crucial role in maintaining a reliable food supply that is supplemented by hunting. Women were heavily involved in the collecting process. Uburu

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subsistence farmers relied on hunting and gathering for their food supply (Uzoamaka, 2022).

Gunpowder Production and Salt Making Industry

It is absolutely correct to posit that women dominated the processes of the salt-making or production in Uburu, while men dominated the processes of gun powder production. Salt making industry was totally left for Uburu women. The salt industry was and is a source of pride to Uburu women, and it gives them sense of belonging. Salt production is relatively a non-seasonal enterprise. During the favourable periods (months of October through March), the production output of Uburu salt tends to be at the peak. To account for this, is the fact that there are little or no rains within this months and the salinity of the brine remains high. Uzoamaka (2022) posited that women who engage in salt production often do not have to undergo the various procedures of filtering, boiling and evaporation repeatedly during the favourable periods. They just fetch the concentrated salt water, boil and evaporate the little water content leaving ready salt for sale or no immediate domestic use. However, during the rainy season, which stretches from the months of April through September, the salt lake is over-flooded by the Esu River, which usually over flow its banks during this season. The over flooding reduce in a comparatively great extent the high salinity of the salt lake.

What the women salt producers do at this period of over-flooding and lower concentration is to fetch the salt water, pour it into the filtering pot, "Ite ochichi" which is already containing dried up muddy salt from the "Onu-ebe". Having poured the less containing salt water, producers would wash out the already stored highly concentrated salt inside the "Ite ochichi". It will be filtered into the "Nja – ugbani" placed below and later boiled and evaporated for real salt (Okpara, 2006).

Uburu men specialized in making gun powder while the women were busy in salt production. Slave trafficking equipment, including Dane guns, was being manufactured at Abiriba, Awka, and Nkwere during the period. 'Nkwere Opia Egbe was the name given to the Nkwere blacksmiths because of their reputation for producing high-quality Dane weapons. People from all across Igboland flocked to Uburu to buy salt and gunpowder, therefore a thriving market emerged. The town was given the name "Adu Nshiegbe" for its prominence in the gunpowder production (Okoro, 2022).

Fishing Industry

The original Uburu residents relied heavily on fishing as a means of subsistence. Uburu is home to several rivers that are used for fishing. When you go fishing, you go out to capture fish. Fish may be captured in both natural and supplied water sources, including lakes, rivers, streams, ponds, canals, and reservoirs. Fishing has played a significant role in Uburu society

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ever since the hunter-gatherer era. It is one of the few methods of food production to have survived the transition from prehistoric to industrial times.

To Offia(2022) Fishing is a popular hobby as well as a source of nourishment for many people. Women in Uburu communities focus more on selling fish and seafood than on catching or preparing it. Women in Uburu fisheries, like women in fisheries across the globe, have always been the backbone of the industry, selling fresh and dried fish on head load at primitive fish markets and door to door. Women make up the majority of the food processing industry, and they are the primary supplier of both sun dried and smoked fish. Odi(2022) deposited that it is common practice to dry items in the sun beside the river. Sun drying of fish was evidently used by fisherman. Sun drying and smoking were not improved upon as processing processes. Women that work alongside their husbands in the fishing industry are often referred to as helpers or auxiliary fishermen because of the tasks they do such as gleaning rudimentary fishing equipment, processing fish, trading seafood, and repairing nets. The pre-harvest and post-harvest processes include women extensively.

Farming and Trading

In traditional Uburu culture, women play a significant role in the economy via trading. Uzoamaka (2022) posits that women in Uburu participate in a wide range of economic

activities in order to provide for their families. The local economy is based on the production of salt, brooms, and ceramics. In both pre- and post-colonial times, the small commerce practiced by the Uburu was thriving, and it was carried out mostly by women. Massive crowds of people travelled to Uburu from all around, presumably in search of the city's renowned salt and gun powder. Since individuals in Uburu were able to sell products and services with little to no restrictions, it quickly grew into a major economic hub. Slaves and horses were only two of the many commodities traded in the Avia Nkwurnoto market in the Uburu district. It was true that in the year 1880 A.D., one horse could buy as many as six adult slaves (Ngene, 2022). The economic ascendancy which Uburu people attained in pre-British days was undoubtedly a consequence of their role as middlemen of the traffic in slaves for the internal as well as for the Trans-Atlantic trade. There is considerable evidence that during the slave trade and before trade in oil replaced trade in slaves, Uburu people were among the 'economic dictator's of the hinterland'. Women contributed and participated in every aspects of the trade between Uburu and her neighbours (Odi, 2002). There was sexual division of labour in traditional Uburu society.

Farming, especially yam production has always been regarded as the exclusive presence of Uburu men. While the men take responsibility for clearing the farmland, the women under

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take to burn the bush and assist in carrying the yam seedlings to their various destinations for planting by the men. Weeding is the duty of women who also provide the vanguard for carrying the proceeds of the harvest, at times by head porter age, to the house and to the markets when there is surplus production. Most farmland is controlled by kindred heads. They cooperatively cultivate farmland and make subsequent allocations according to seniority. (Chukwu, 2022).

Pottery and Weaving

Weaving and pottery production was a major economic driver in pre-colonial Uburu. Women in Uburu community were heavily involved. Before the British colonial era, weaving was a primary activity for women in Uburu, as it had been in numerous communities throughout Igbo nation. The traditional fabrics woven by Uburu's women were in great demand both inside and outside the country. In pre-British Igboland, traditional woven fabrics were usually utilized for festivals, rituals, anniversaries, and other such occasions. Basket weaving was another common activity for Uburu women. The raffia palm was used to make a variety of useful products, including baskets, brooms for cleaning thatches, fishing traps, and preserving pans (Uzoamaka, 2022).

Cooking pots, water cans, trays, storage tanks, and other clay utensils were used in pre-colonial Uburu households and workplaces alike. Herbalists, diviners, and other traditional

medical practitioners in Igbo country also made use of the goods for spiritual purposes. During the pre-colonial era, the Uburu pottery industry employed many women, and its wares were in great demand thanks to the patronage of shoppers doing business in the many marketplaces around Igbo nation.

Politics and Governance

Women in pre-colonial Uburu politics were not afforded the same rights as males. At the Aja Ama-Eze, the ancient village square, women were not permitted to speak out on any of the issues being discussed. Okoro (2022) deposited that Aja Ama-Eze is a sacred place and only those who are holy and pure are allowed to speak or add to a conversation taking place there. The fact that women have such a quick tongue means they keep nothing to themselves. There are concerns that Uburu would lose their sense of corporate survival if outsiders are allowed to participate in vital discussions. First and foremost, they might potentially betray the community by disclosing sensitive information. As a result, they were never allowed to participate in the discussions held at Aja Ama-Eze to address the concerns of the community as a whole. If a woman must speak, however, she is expected to put her right hand on the man's shoulder to show that he is the one doing the talking (Ngene, 2022).

However, women banded together to form sociopolitical organizations in an effort to increase their voice in communal decision-

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making and politics. Uburu politics were heavily influenced by the Ndi Uyom Uburu (women's group). Ndi Uyom Uburu persuaded the men to end the practice of ordering women and did not hold back from speaking out against the men's mistreatment of the land. When men were afraid of Ndi Uyom, they started making better choices. The Ogoo-Nwanyi title holders made up another influential social and political group of women in Uburu politics. In the Uburu culture, Ogoo-Nwanyi is the greatest award bestowed to a deserving female. This honorific, known as Ogoo-Nwanyi in the Uburu traditional system, has been bestowed to deserving ladies for ages.

Obasi (2017) posits that the Ogoo-Nwanyi title breaks down barriers by operating under the no-holds-barred premise while actively working to eliminate the gender gap, which is often seen as having ensconced a deeply ingrained restrictive conventional system. This is supported by the fact that the Ogoo-Nwanyi title holders are often regarded as having had a position of great influence within the local society. Whatever they say is accepted by the whole village and community if there is a conundrum in the decision making process. The ruling of an Ogoo-Nwanyi title holder is respected and followed as if it were the law.

Obasi (2017) further stressed that an Ogoo-Nwanyi title holder exudes authority, eloquence, self-esteem, and confidence stemming from some cogent attachment whenever she speaks

publicly on any issue pertaining to the socio-cultural milieu. And in this setting, her gender is irrelevant since her remarks would be recognized without resorting to gender awareness caused by male chauvinism. As a result, the Ogoo-Nwanyi title and practice are the only traditional myth and legend in the Uburu socio-cultural context and traditional mythology that both serve to bridge the gender gap and institutionalize gender equality. The reality of this is evident in the fact that women who had the Ogoo-Nwanyi title were treated with equal respect and dignity by their male counterparts when they speak among them.

Women in colonial Uburu society were relegated to the background due to shifts in gender roles brought on by colonization. According to Yusuf (as cited in Badejo, 1985), during the colonial era, Nigerian women were less politically engaged. That's because colonial rule introduced ideas like "European Patriarchy into Nigerian society," which had a profound effect on gender roles.

It has been argued that the colonial era, with its promotion of predominantly male-dominated social and political systems, was the genesis of the structures of inequality that have led to discrimination against women. It is undeniable that mechanisms of inequality existed before colonizing, but it was only when they were codified as new legal institutions that they became really entrenched. Women were discriminated against in several areas at the

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period, including the economy (loans were not made available to them) and education (girls were forced to choose courses like home economics rather than ones that would improve their employability). One of the most prominent areas where colonialism negatively impacted women was in leadership and administration. First and foremost, until the 1950s, women were denied the right to vote, making it impossible for them to have an active role in or make a significant contribution to the political process.

While Uburu women were not actively involved in party politics, they were influential outside of the parties as supporters of different parties and advocates for women's rights. For Uburu women, the "time of awakening" that followed the end of colonial rule signified the beginning of their participation in politics after decades of silence. For many, the return of women's voting rights is the catalyst for this awakening. With the granting of franchise to women, they started showing interest to be part of the new government. In the first republic, women's political participation was very limited, especially in decision-making roles and high-level appointments. Unfortunately, by the time of the second republic (1979–1983), few women were appointed to positions of power.

The constitution in effect at the time (1979) explicitly protected the rights of women, forbidding discrimination on the basis of gender and specifying that women over the age of 21 may both cast and receive votes (Badejo, 1985).

Unfortunately, the amount of women's engagement was still affected by socio-cultural and colonial impact or underlying issues. Given the foregoing, it's not surprising that few influential women emerged during the second republic, particularly within political parties. Due to the military coup that occurred on December 31st, 1983, the country's political structure was altered once again, and the previously recorded success soon faded. The military rule's quota system for women's appointment to government positions was a pivotal moment for women's political empowerment. It has been mandated by the federal government that every state's executive council include a minimum of one woman (Attoe, 2002).

As was to be anticipated, the new spirit of democracy, the restoration of civilian government, and the growth of women in many fields has led to an increase in the number of women in the political scene since the establishment of the fourth republic on May 29, 1999.

The Impact of Women in the Development of Uburu Community in the Pre-Colonial Period

Uburu women had crucial roles in society and the economy before European colonization. Women took active part in farming, first for their own survival and subsequently for profit. When the farmland was covered in a dense forest and large trees needed to be chopped

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down, it is reasonable to assume that men did this work.

Okoro (2022) stated that groups of women (often between five and ten individuals) would organize to do chores on each other's farms on a weekly basis. Cocoyam (Edeh), yam (Ji), cassava, maize, vegetables, pepper, and plantain were some of the crops grown. In this way, women were essential to the success of the agricultural sector. These ladies used some of the money they made from selling their crops to invest in their farms, their children's education, and the improvement of their neighbourhood. Women also made ceramics and woven mats, textiles, and baskets when they weren't farming. The fiber from the raffia palm was woven into all manner of useful objects, including storage trays, fishing nets, mats, and brooms for sweeping roof thatch.

Women also presided over the salt industry and commerce. Women ran the entire salt business because men were only allowed to perform religious rites, and vice versa. Making a living from the sale of palm goods, salt, and agricultural products was a welcome sideline. Palm fruits were used to make palm oil, commonly known as red oil, and palm kernels was also used to make palm kernel oil, which has medicinal value and is used for body beatification (Uzoamaka, 2022). Women in pre-colonial Uburu culture had positions of great economic importance. They were very proactive, enterprising, and dynamic in all of the economic

operations that ensured the Uburu people's continued existence. The women in Uburu community played an essential part in the community's economic life, contributing to the organization and running of regular and daily markets, running food stalls and roadside stands, and making house-to-house sales.

During the pre-colonial era in Uburu, the traditional pottery industry was one of the most prominent indigenous industrial businesses that relied heavily on the labour of women. Utensils of all shapes and sizes, from cooking pots to water cans to trays to storage tanks to weavers' and dyers' pots were among the most common products of the Uburu pottery industry, which helped to advance the local economy. As a pre-colonial society based on agriculture, food processing was an essential element of the economy in Uburu. As a result, women played a larger role in the food processing business than men. Uburu women used to process a wide variety of agricultural goods before colonization, including yam, cassava, vegetables, fruits, palm oil, palm kernels, corn, smoked fish, pepper, garri, etc. In pre-colonial Uburu society, women typically arranged for the distribution of processed foods to be sold at regular markets and by hawkers. Thus, the Uburu women folk engaged in an important economic activity in the form of food processing, which contributed to the growth and development of the Uburu economy before colonial rule.

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Livestock farming was a significant economic activity in pre-colonial Uburu. Goat and sheep herding, poultry farming, and fishing were all important parts of the Uburu economy. Women in Uburu community were said to have played an important role in all aspects of livestock production, especially in the rearing of sheep, goats, and chickens. Domestic sub-sector of pre-colonial Uburu economy benefited greatly from Uburu women's participation in the marketing of domestic animals and poultry products/brands like eggs, hens, cocks, and chickens.

In intergroup relations and peace building, Uburu women promoted harmonious intergroup relations between Uburu and her neighbors through trade, intermarriages and cultural ties. Women performed social roles like procreating, nurturing and cementing ties with Uburu neighbors during conflicts and peace times (Michael & Chidi 2022). Despite the fact that Uburu women did not have the same access to politics as men, they were nonetheless very engaged in the political process. They were involved in creating the policy. Their political contributions came about because they were able to persuade their husbands, brothers, and other male relatives to change their minds about crucial issues facing the community. Women played significant roles in pre-colonial Uburu society, the most notable of which was likely the early socialisation of children. Children were at least until the age of seven, in the exclusive care

of their mothers. Children were taught the language, norms, myth and legend etc of the community. This was carried on basically via folk-tales, stories and songs.

The Impact of Women in the Development of Uburu Community in the Colonial Period

Uburu women responded to the challenges of new political, economic and social order arising from colonial rule. The adjustments required in coping with these challenges made women perform new roles. Ngene (2002) posits that colonial Uburu society never saw or treated women as sexual instruments or people whose education ends in the kitchen. They were in most cases treated as equals. Little wonder that as far back as the 1940s a good number of Uburu women had already acquired western education and were already employed as teachers. They impacted positively on the educational sector of Uburu community.

In the colonial period, Uburu women were at the heart of development. Women were in control of subsistence agriculture, bearing and early child socialization, doing domestic labour and taking crucial part trading etc. Women played critical role in the economy of colonial Uburu where they were producers of food. They were also involved in food processing, childcare, sanitation and the entire range of survival needs of the community. Even though palm oil production dominated the colonial era economy, Uburu women also engaged in many

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other aspects of economic endeavors to give sustenance to the subsistence economy and economic stabilization in the family and community. They helped to bring women's and welfare matters in an organized manner to the enlightened public. They thus sensitized the enlightened public about women welfare, suggested solutions and agitated for their implementation.

The Impact of Women in the Development of Uburu Community in the Post-Colonial Period

Women are versatile in community development. The stability, progress and long term development of communities have been the central roles of women throughout the human race. The achievements of Uburu women across the political, socio-economic and cultural spheres cannot be overemphasized. It is axiomatic to posit that there is a linkage between women and community development.

According to Offia (2022) women are crucial to progress. Women have a crucial role in the continuation of life on Earth. This makes them the source of humanity's life force. They played vital role in shaping their children personalities as their first educator, peacemaker, beauty icon, and primary caretaker. In reality, Women are mothers of the human race.

The contemporary political growth of the Uburu kingdom has been aided by the participation of Uburu women, who have voted for worthy candidates, sang and clapped their hands during

campaigns, and even ran for elective positions of the state. Mrs. Marian Babangida's, advocacy for women's issues and interests, as well as her creation of the National Commission for Women and ministerial portfolio for women affairs, the Better Life for Rural Women Programmes, have all contributed to the advancement of women in the Uburu community.

Women in Uburu organized a wide variety of groups to help them fulfill their vital responsibilities in community improvement. Such as; self- help Women Organization, Uyom Uburu Organization, Farming Support Programme, Uburu Women Development Association, Umu Ada (Daughters) Women Organization, Uburu Women Political Stakeholders among others. Building maternity homes, community centres, culverts, bridges, providing water boreholes, supplying grinding machines, opening health centres, and immunizing children with the help of the World Health Organization and the Ministry of Health were just a few of the many development projects they undertook. Many Uburu residents aspired to influential political roles so that they could work to end harmful cultural traditions like female genital mutilation and the practice of marrying off young girls.

Conclusion

Findings have shown that Uburu women played significant roles in community development. Women offer unique and strong viewpoint to

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the negotiation table, and they have a long history of dedication to peace-building, community development, and post-conflict rehabilitation. These results informed the following inferences from the study; marginalization, discrimination suppression and imposing of regulations and rules against women are observed in the study. Notwithstanding, the emancipation of women should be the priority of the community including women themselves for the effective role in community development. Women should be active in all the roles they are required to play for community development, women were found to be the primary funders of community development programmes in Uburu community. Therefore, they should not let up on their pursuit of the worthy goals, despite the restrictions placed on the Uburu women,

historical records show that it was the women who set the agenda for communal and economic development. Apart from writing women into Uburu community history, this study has made an attempt at analyzing gender roles disparity in Uburu community, as well as the impact of women in Uburu community development. It highlights women's importance not only as a passive breed but also as community developers in creating new developments, in resistance to and collision with oppression, research into women's roles in the development of Uburu has contributed to and widened our understanding of African realities in a variety of ways. This research adds to the growing chorus calling for measures to promote women's full and equal involvement in the nation's economic and other critical sectors in order to foster sustainable development.

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Primary Sources (Oral Interviews)

S/N	NAME	AGE	SEX	OCCUPATION	HOME/TOWN	PLACE OF INTERVIEW	DATE OF INTERVIEW
1	Obasi Emmanuel	60	M	Lecturer	Umuobuna - Uburu	Abakaliki	3 rd June, 2022
2	Ngene Ajaegu	60	M	Lecturer	Umuanem-Uburu	Uburu	1 st June, 2022
3	Odi Umahi	38	M	Public Servant	Amenu - Uburu	Uburu	1 st June, 2022
4	Offia Chukwu	65	F	Farmer	Umuchima - Uburu	Uburu	1 st June, 2022
5	Okoro	46	M	Farmer/Civil	Ogwu - Uburu	Uburu	12 th July,

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	Innocent			Servant				2022
6	Uzoamaka Chukwu	70	F	Former Salt Maker	Umuchima - Uburu		Uburu	12 th July, 2022

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